

MEDICAL AND SOCIAL ASPECTS OF REPRODUCTIVE HEALTH OF CHILDREN AGED 8 TO 15 YEARS

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ABSTRACT

In conditions of social tension and stratification of society, a sharp drop in the standard of living of the population, it is children and adolescents who become one of the most vulnerable groups of the population. But it is adolescents who are the reproductive, intellectual, economic, social, political and cultural reserve of society. This determines the huge social significance of their health.

Against the background of the transformation of the socio-economic and political structure in our country, there is a steady trend towards deterioration in the health indicators of children and adolescents. Thus, statistics indicate that from 50 to 75% of girls have health disorders that may negatively affect their reproductive function in the future. We must not forget that the leading factors determining the process of formation of reproductive health of children and adolescents are their living conditions and lifestyle.

Unfortunately, the socio-economic changes that have taken place have had a negative impact on the change of stereotypes of behavior among young people - interest in sports has decreased, there is a lack of necessary knowledge and social motivation to preserve and strengthen one's own health, at the same time, bad habits have become widespread, the frequency of premarital sexual relations has increased. Numerous studies have noted destructive trends in the reproductive health of adolescents, which in the future may be one of the most important reasons for maintaining a low birth rate, high infant mortality rates, pathology of pregnancy and childbirth. In the light of the current priorities in the field of healthcare being implemented, the problems of the reproductive health of adolescent girls and the preservation of their reproductive potential are of particular importance.

Currently, there is no doubt that the functioning of the reproductive system of women is largely determined by its timely and harmonious development during puberty. However, in the first decade of the XXI century, the reproductive potential of adolescent girls had stable and mostly unfavorable characteristics, among which should be highlighted:

- high prevalence of reproductively significant bad habits;
- a large percentage of deviations in physical, sexual and psychosexual development;
- high level of somatic and gynecological morbidity; - formation of inadequate reproductive attitudes;

- low level of sex education and contraceptive activity;
- high frequency of teenage pregnancy with a predominant outcome in abortion.

-The most significant factors affecting the reproductive health of adolescents are risky sexual behavior, an increase in the number of diseases of the reproductive system, infection with sexually transmitted diseases, pregnancies and abortions in adolescence, a low level of knowledge about contraceptive methods. Sexual behavior is closely related to reproductive health, being in fact one of its main components. During the last century, there has been a tendency to decrease the age of the beginning of sexual life.

A review of modern foreign and domestic studies on this topic shows that the proportion of sexually active young people is increasing, and the average age of first sexual contact is constantly decreasing. So over the past decades, there has been a steady trend towards a decrease in the age of sexual debut, which, according to anonymous surveys, reaches 14.5 years. The sexual activity of adolescents is influenced by a number of factors, among which the socio-economic situation, the nature of family relations, the influence of peers and the media can be distinguished. At the same time, increased sexual activity is associated with several types of risks for adolescents, including unplanned pregnancies, abortions, illegitimate births, sexual exploitation and maternal mortality. One of the most important social and medical problems is also the increase in the incidence of sexually transmitted diseases. The increased risk of infection of adolescents with these diseases is associated with a variety of behavioral, biological and psychosocial factors, among which sexual activity is considered as the most critical risk factor. It should also be noted that today school graduates have a disdainful attitude towards their own health and the health of others, they have a low level of perception of health problems as personally significant, there is an insufficient level of knowledge about a healthy lifestyle, ways to preserve and strengthen their health. Teenagers are alarmed and frightened by the pubertal changes and changes in psychological processes that occur with them. But along with complex, sometimes unpredictable features, such important qualities as the desire to know oneself and others, the search for identity, the desire to assert oneself, the formation of moral beliefs and reflection are formed in adolescence. At the same time, in modern curricula of general education schools, for example, reproductive health issues are clearly not given enough attention. The period of protracted organizational and legal transformations that have affected all aspects of the educational process, the process of obtaining a quality education is becoming more and more time-consuming. Therefore, education will perform the function of health promotion only if health is not only taught, but will be able to make it the main need and lifestyle of all participants in the educational process. The education of children to take care of their own health, the formation of skills and abilities to preserve and strengthen it is overwhelmingly formalized. The established practice reduces this work at school to lectures, the main content of which is information about the clinical picture, diagnosis and treatment of diseases. As a rule, they are read by medical professionals, but they do not always know the methodology of teaching and educating healthy behavior, methods of forming students' positive motivation to preserve health. The structure of interpersonal social support, including the number of relationships and the quality of the system of relations of an individual with the immediate

environment, in which the family plays an important role, can contribute to or hinder the development of a teenager's personal preventive resource.

From the standpoint of modern pedagogical science, educational activity is a system of actions (mental and practical), the implementation of which ensures the assimilation of knowledge, mastery of skills and abilities, their application to solving various tasks. The low level of reproductive health and medical culture of modern adolescents determines, in turn, the need to introduce new programs of sexual education of students into the system of domestic school education, since the current curricula of school courses do not correspond to the age characteristics and educational needs of students in matters of preserving and strengthening reproductive health. Unfortunately, at the moment, the level of theoretical knowledge about reproductive health is extremely low and cannot ensure the preservation of reproductive health of adolescents in practical life and requires qualitative improvement. It is obvious that the strategic priority of the state policy in the social sphere should be the formation and development of values of a healthy lifestyle.

The above circumstances allow us to conclude that the development and implementation of methods for the formation of students' knowledge on the preservation and strengthening of reproductive health, as a component of healthy lifestyle, is an urgent pedagogical problem. In accordance with this, educational institutions face a whole range of new tasks that require urgent decisions. The most important of them was the development of specific methodological approaches aimed at forming the knowledge of schoolchildren of various age categories about reproductive health. At the same time, the modern methodology should contribute to the formation of an integral system of theoretical knowledge and practical skills of students of secondary educational institutions for the preservation and strengthening of reproductive health. It should be based on the personal interest of students, taking into account the individual and age needs of schoolchildren, the widespread use of interdisciplinary connections, interactive forms of education and modern information technologies, as well as a clear practical orientation of the acquired knowledge about reproductive health.

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